

SOCIAL MEDIA UTILIZATION IN SUPPORTING ACADEMIC WRITING SKILLS AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the utilization of social media in supporting the academic writing skills of the selected college students enrolled in Purposive Communication SY 2022-2023 at Metro Dumaguete College. It utilized the descriptive-correlational research design and employed the random sampling technique in identifying the 140 respondents. It also utilized a validated questionnaire and used weighted mean and Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Coefficient for the treatment of the data. The salient findings revealed that the extent of utilization of Facebook and YouTube in supporting students' academic writing skills are both "high". In contrast, the extent of utilization of TikTok is "moderate". Moreover, the findings also revealed that the students perceived Facebook to have a "high" valuable support in their academic writing skills regarding grammar, spelling, vocabulary, and cohesion. On the other hand, students perceived YouTube to have a "very high" valuable support in their academic writing skills regarding grammar, spelling, vocabulary, and cohesion. In contrast, students perceived TikTok to have "moderate" valuable support in their academic writing skills in terms of grammar and cohesion, "high" in spelling, and "very high" in vocabulary. Furthermore, it was found that there is a significant and strong relationship between the utilization of the aforementioned social media platforms and their perceived support of the aforementioned students' academic writing skills. Lastly, it was found that there is no significant relationship between the sex, age, and location of the students and their extent of utilization of social media platforms.

Keywords: *academic writing skills; social media utilization; value of support*

INTRODUCTION

The exponential growth of digital technology facilitates education through the utilization of various social media platforms. In the world of academia, social media provides authentic teaching-learning experiences beyond the classroom setting (Al-Jarrah et al., 2019), providing students with more exposure to socializing among peers, friends, teachers, families, and even English native speakers (Yunus et al., 2019). Moreover, social media allows students to explore and practice the English language through virtual discussions of relevant issues. Hence, it supports the development of students' English writing skills, such as grammar, spelling, vocabulary, and abbreviation (Al-Jarrah et al., 2019). Although social media have played a vital role in students' academic success (Bond & Bedenlier, 2019), it is also undoubtedly becoming the means of spreading peculiar languages known as Gen Z slang, especially for Gen Zs who are known as "digital natives". Consequently, communication barriers and confusions among older generations occur (Alruthaya et al., 2021).

In the Philippine educational setting, the English language is the primary medium of instruction at the tertiary levels, both in public and private learning institutions, as mandated by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED). Although English is taught as early as the primary level in the Philippines, English proficiency among Filipino learners is continuously declining. An international company, Education First (EF), reports the country's consecutive drop in the English Proficiency Index (EF EPI), ranking from the top 15 in previous years to 20th, 27th, 18th, and 22nd, respectively, from 2019 through 2022. While the country's English Proficiency continuously declines, it has remained the top active social media user globally in the latest digital 2022 report by We Are Social.

Undoubtedly, social media is a venue for English language learners to improve their writing skills through academic research and social interaction with people from different backgrounds globally (Tomas & Dulin, 2021). It is a vital skill to master, requiring a set of lexical and grammatical rules (Rao, 2019). While the effects of social media utilization on students' English language proficiency have been widely examined (Ariantini et al., 2021; Tomas & Dulin, 2021; Aziz et al., 2019), this study highlights the students' value of support provided by social media for their academic writing skills, especially considering the drastic growth of TikTok users. As social media provide easy access to communication (Page et al., 2022), the spread of Gen Z's peculiar languages has become unstoppable (Jeresano & Carretero, 2022). Hence, the question of whether social media support writing skills among students or is a hindrance remains.

After more than two years of teaching at the college level, the researcher has observed college students' poor academic writing performance. The researcher also observed students' integration of Gen Z slang into their academic writing. For these reasons, the researcher conducted this study to determine whether or not social media provide support students' academic writing skills.

Research Questions

The study aimed to examine the utilization of social media in supporting academic writing skills among students. It specifically sought to answer the following questions:

1. To what extent do students utilize the following social media platforms as support in their academic writing:
 - 1.1 Facebook;
 - 1.2 YouTube; and
 - 1.3 TikTok?
2. What is the perceived value of support provided by social media platforms on students' academic writing skills in the following areas:
 - 2.1 grammar;
 - 2.2 spelling;
 - 2.3 vocabulary; and
 - 2.4 cohesion?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent to which students utilize social media platforms and its perceived value of support on students' academic writing?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the extent to which students utilize social media platforms as support in their academic writing and the following profile items:
 - 4.1 sex;
 - 4.2 age; and
 - 4.3 location?

METHODOLOGY

Data and Respondents

The respondents of the study were the college students of Metro Dumaguete College enrolled in Purposive Communication subject for the Academic Year 2022-2023. Of the 215 total populations, there were 140 sampled students. These students were chosen through random sampling, wherein every second person in the student list was selected.

In gathering the data, the researcher utilized a researcher-made questionnaire based on the researcher's readings from different scholarly articles related to the study. The items were checked by the three experts in the field of English for content validity. One of these experts holds a doctorate degree, while the other two have a master's degree specializing in English. All these experts are currently teaching in their respective schools in Negros Oriental.

To ensure item reliability, a dry run was conducted on the 30 college students of Metro Dumaguete College. The items were tested for their reliability using Cronbach's alpha test. This test is regarded as the most suitable type for survey research where items are not scored right or wrong, and each item could have different answers (McMillan &

Schumacher, 2001). This was calculated to verify the internal consistency and reliability of the items. It measures the extent to which all the variables in the scale are positively related to each other, and its theoretical value varies from 0 to 1. Higher values of alpha are more desirable, and a value of 0.70 is considered acceptable. The following are the results of Cronbach's Alpha Test: 0.902 for social media utilization, 0.887 for grammar, 0.904 for spelling, 0.901 for vocabulary, and 0.908 for cohesion. All values are greater than 0.70; hence, all items are reliable.

The researcher implemented all the necessary ethical considerations in the entire duration of this study. Since humans were chosen as the study's respondents, the confidentiality of information was observed and dignity was upheld. Furthermore, minimizing potential risks to the respondents was always observed.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

The researcher utilized the following tools in analyzing and interpreting the study's data:

Weighted Mean. This was used to get the (a) extent of social media utilization and (b) value of support provided by social media platforms to students' writing skills.

Spearman rank correlation coefficient. This was utilized to identify the degree of relationship between the students' extent of social media utilization and the perceived value of support for students' academic writing and the following variables: students' profile.

Measures

Dependent variable. The dependent variable considers the perceived extent of the value of support provided by social media platforms to students' writing skills. It was measured using the weighted mean with the following options: never (5 scores), seldom (4 scores), sometimes (3 scores), often (2 scores), and always (1 score).

Independent variable. The secondary independent variable includes the sex, age, and location of the students and the primary independent variable is the utilization of social media. The researcher had the presumption that the secondary independent variable might be related to the extent of social media utilization. She also hypothesized that the student's utilization of social media has something to do with their perceived extent of social media support on their academic writing skills.

RESULTS

Table 1.1
Extent to which Students Utilize Social Media Platforms as Support in Their Academic Writing (n = 140)

I use social media...	Platform	w \bar{x}	VD	EoU
1. To study when I write a formal document.	Facebook	3.54	O	H

	YouTube	3.44	O	H
	TikTok	2.79	S	M
2. To disseminate information.	Facebook	3.92	O	H
	Youtube	2.98	S	M
	TikTok	2.69	S	M
3. To research unfamiliar topics.	Facebook	3.31	S	M
	YouTube	4.03	O	H
	TikTok	2.99	S	M
4. To broaden my knowledge of the current lesson before completing any assignment.	Facebook	3.16	S	M
	YouTube	3.84	O	H
	TikTok	2.59	S	L
5. To verify facts or information I am not sure of.	Facebook	3.41	O	H
	YouTube	3.86	O	H
	TikTok	2.78	S	M
6. To engage in discussions on social media which helps me develop my writing skills.	Facebook	3.51	O	H
	YouTube	3.88	O	H
	TikTok	2.81	S	M
7. To improve my understanding of terms I use from videos or written materials on social media.	Facebook	3.75	O	H
	YouTube	4.27	O	H
	TikTok	3.26	S	M
8. To extend my learning beyond classroom instruction.	Facebook	3.33	S	M
	YouTube	3.79	O	H
	TikTok	2.81	S	M
9. To overcome my fear of communicating with others.	Facebook	4.13	O	H
	YouTube	3.36	S	M
	TikTok	3.18	S	M
10. To clear my confusion, which may hinder my academic writing skills.	Facebook	3.60	O	H
	YouTube	3.90	O	H
	TikTok	2.94	S	M
Composite	Facebook	3.57	O	H
	YouTube	3.74	O	H
	TikTok	2.88	S	M

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Manifestation (EoE)
	4.21 – 5.00	Always (A)	Very High (VH)
	3.41 – 4.20	Often (O)	High (H)
	2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes (S)	Moderate (M)
	1.81 – 2.60	Seldom (S)	Low (L)
	1.00 – 1.80	Never (N)	Very Low (VL)

Table 1.1 presents the data on the extent of students' social media utilization on their academic writing skills. As shown in the table, students utilized Facebook and YouTube at a "high" extent with a composite weighted mean of 3.57 and 3.74, respectively, while students utilized TikTok at a "moderate" extent with a composite weighted mean of 2.88 in supporting their academic writing skills.

Table 2.1
Perceived Value of Support provided by Social Media Platforms on Students' Academic Writing Skills in Terms of Grammar (n = 140)

<i>The following social media...</i>	<i>w\bar{x}</i>	<i>VD</i>	<i>EVoS</i>
1. Help me check whether my composition is grammatically correct or wrong.			
• Facebook	3.61	A	H

• YouTube	4.24	SA	VH
• TikTok	3.07	MA	M
2. Provide videos about rules in grammar including proper punctuation which I can apply in my academic writing.			
• Facebook	3.79	A	H
• YouTube	4.52	SA	VH
• TikTok	3.46	A	H
3. Provide opportunities to practice my writing skills.			
• Facebook	3.69	A	H
• YouTube	4.21	SA	VH
• TikTok	3.24	MA	M
4. Motivate me to improve my composition with correct grammar by engaging in real-life discussions.			
• Facebook	3.86	A	H
• YouTube	4.34	SA	VH
• TikTok	3.44	A	H
5. Boost my confidence in writing with correct grammar.			
• Facebook	3.81	A	H
• YouTube	4.26	SA	VH
• TikTok	3.46	A	H
Composite			
• Facebook	3.75	A	H
• YouTube	4.32	SA	VH
• TikTok	3.34	MA	M
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent Value of Support (EVoS)
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)	High (H)
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree (MA)	Moderate (M)
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)	Low (L)
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Low (VL)

Table 2.1 unveils the perceived value of support provided by social media platforms on students' academic writing skills in terms of grammar. It can be drawn from the data that students have varying perceptions of the value of support provided by social media in terms of grammar. Of the three social media, students perceive YouTube to have a "very high" value of support on their academic writing skills in terms of grammar, with a composite weighted mean of 4.32. On the other hand, students perceive Facebook to have a "high" value of support on their academic writing skills in terms of grammar, with a composite mean of 3.75. Lastly, students perceive TikTok to have a "moderate" value of support on their academic writing, with a composite mean of 3.34. As reflected in the weighted mean, the values range from 3.07 to 4.52. These data infer that students are aware of the educational value of social media in supporting their writing skills in terms of grammar, particularly on YouTube.

Table 2.2

Perceived Value of Support provided by Social Media Platforms on Students' Academic Writing Skills in Terms of Spelling (n = 140)

<i>The following social media...</i>	$\bar{w}\bar{x}$	VD	EVoS
1. Help me check the correct spelling of unfamiliar words.			
2.			
• Facebook	3.76	A	H
• YouTube	4.31	SA	VH
• TikTok	3.51	A	H
3. Help me identify the different homophonic words that are commonly misused.			
• Facebook	3.64	A	H
• YouTube	4.14	A	H
• TikTok	3.36	MA	M
4. Help me review the most commonly misspelled words.			
• Facebook	3.71	A	H
• YouTube	4.32	SA	VH
• TikTok	3.34	MA	M
5. Help me study the correct spelling of words to avoid miscommunication.			
• Facebook	3.86	A	H
• YouTube	4.38	SA	VH
• TikTok	3.46	A	H
6. Provide possible alternative words whenever I do not know the correct spelling of certain words.			
• Facebook	3.84	A	H
• YouTube	4.43	SA	VH
• TikTok	3.45	A	H
Composite			
• Facebook	3.76	A	H
• YouTube	4.32	SA	VH
• TikTok	3.42	A	H
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent Value of Support (EVoS)
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)	High (H)
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree (MA)	Moderate (M)
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)	Low (L)
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Low (VL)

Table 2.2 presents the perceived value of support provided by social media platforms on students' academic writing skills in terms of spelling. As shown in the table, students perceived YouTube to have a "very high" value of support for their academic writing in terms of spelling, with a composite weighted mean of 4.32. On the other hand, students perceived both Facebook and TikTok to have a "high" value of support for their academic writing in terms of spelling, with a composite weighted mean of 3.76 and 3.42, respectively.

Table 2.3

Perceived Value of Support provided by Social Media Platforms on Students' Academic Writing Skills in Terms of Vocabulary (n = 140)

<i>The following social media...</i>	$w\bar{x}$	VD	EVoS
1. Allow me to search the definition of an unfamiliar word.			
• Facebook	3.59	A	H
• YouTube	4.40	SA	VH
• TikTok	3.34	MA	M
2. Allow me to search for similar words or synonyms of a word.			
• Facebook	3.67	A	H
• YouTube	4.45	SA	VH
• TikTok	3.38	MA	M
3. Enrich my vocabulary in order to avoid redundancy of words.			
• Facebook	3.65	A	H
• YouTube	4.39	SA	VH
• TikTok	3.38	MA	M
4. Increase my exposure to familiar and unfamiliar words.			
• Facebook	3.82	A	H
• YouTube	4.44	SA	VH
• TikTok	3.54	A	H
Broaden and provide references when reading difficult terminologies.			
• Facebook	3.72	A	H
• YouTube	4.26	SA	VH
• TikTok	3.43	A	H
Composite			
• Facebook	3.69	A	H
• YouTube	4.39	SA	VH
• TikTok	3.41	A	H

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent Value of Support (EVoS)
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)	High (H)
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree (MA)	Moderate (M)
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)	Low (L)
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Low (VL)

Table 2.3 reflects the perceived value of support provided by social media platforms on students' academic writing skills in terms of vocabulary. As shown in the table, students perceived YouTube to have a "very high" value of support for their academic writing in terms of vocabulary, with a composite weighted mean of 4.39. On the other hand, students perceived both Facebook and TikTok to have a "high" value of support on students' academic writing skills in terms of vocabulary, with a composite weighted mean of 3.69 and 3.41, respectively.

Table 2.4

Perceived Value of Support provided by Social Media Platforms on Students' Academic Writing Skills in Terms of Cohesion (n = 140)

<i>The following social media...</i>	$w\bar{x}$	VD	EVoS
1. Help me find adverbial words or phrases to link-ideas within sentences, other parts of sentences, or paragraphs			
• Facebook	3.75	A	H

• YouTube	4.30	SA	VH
• TikTok	3.40	MA	M
2. Help me find conjunctions to link ideas within sentence/s, other parts of sentences, or paragraphs			
• Facebook	3.67	A	H
• YouTube	4.24	SA	VH
• TikTok	3.30	MA	M
3. Provide information on how to write concise sentences to avoid redundancy and repetition of words or phrases, which may confuse the reader.			
• Facebook	3.59	A	H
• YouTube	4.36	SA	VH
• TikTok	3.36	MA	M
4. Provide written materials on the correct usage of transitions or signals to link the sequence of an idea to the next.			
• Facebook	3.56	A	H
• YouTube	4.33	SA	VH
• TikTok	3.31	MA	M
5. Provide video presentations on how to logically organize and appropriately sequence ideas in a composition.			
• Facebook	3.79	A	H
• YouTube	4.46	SA	VH
• TikTok	3.51	A	H
 Composite			
• Facebook	3.67	A	H
• YouTube	4.34	SA	VH
• TikTok	3.38	MA	M

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent Value of Support (EVoS)
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)	High (H)
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree (MA)	Moderate (M)
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)	Low (L)
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Low (VL)

Table 2.4 depicts the perceived value of support provided by social media platforms on students' academic writing skills in terms of cohesion. As shown in the table, students perceived YouTube to have a "very high" value of support for their academic writing in terms of cohesion, with a composite weighted mean of 4.34. On the other hand, students perceived Facebook to have a "high" value of support for their academic writing in terms of cohesion, with a composite weighted mean of 3.67. Lastly, students perceived TikTok to have a "moderate" value of support for their academic writing in terms of cohesion, with a composite weighted mean of 3.38. It can be drawn that students have varying perceptions of the value of support provided by social media on their academic writing in terms of cohesion. These findings imply the crucial role of social media in developing students' cohesive writing.

Table 3
Relationship between the Extent to which Students Utilize Social Media Platforms and Its Perceived Value of Support on Students' Academic Writing (n = 140)

Variables	r_s	p-value	Decision	Remark
Facebook Utilization and Perceived Value of Support in Students'...				
Grammar	0.646	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Spelling	0.598	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Vocabulary	0.618	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Cohesion	0.637	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
YouTube Utilization and Perceived Value of Support in Students'...				
Grammar	0.514	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Spelling	0.572	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Vocabulary	0.774	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Cohesion	0.710	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
TikTok Utilization and Perceived Value of Support in Students'...				
Grammar	0.747	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Spelling	0.666	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Vocabulary	0.653	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Cohesion	0.653	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant

Level of significance = 0.05

Legend:	Value of r	Strength of Relationship (Statistical Correlation, 2009)
Between	± 0.50 to ± 1.00	± strong relationship
Between	± 0.30 to ± 0.49	± moderate relationship
Between	± 0.10 to ± 0.29	± weak relationship
Between	± 0.01 to ± 0.09	± very weak relationship

Table 3 reveals the data in identifying the relationship between the extent to which students utilize social media in terms of Facebook, YouTube, and TikTok and its perceived value of support on students' academic writing. Using the Spearman Rank Order Correlation (r_s), it is shown that all p-values (0.000) are less than the level of significance (0.05). In addition, all r_s -values are within the range of 0.50 to 1.0. These findings allow the rejection of the null hypothesis. This means there is a significant and strong relationship between the utilization of the aforementioned social media platforms

and their perceived support on students' academic writing in terms of grammar, spelling, vocabulary, and cohesion. This further implies that the greater the utilization of the three social media platforms, the higher the perceived value of support in students' grammar, spelling, vocabulary, and cohesion.

Table 4

Relationship between the Profile of the Students and the Extent to which They Utilize Social Media Platforms as Support in Their Academic Writing (n = 140)

Variables	Comp. Value	p-value	Decision	Remark
Sex and Extent of Utilization of Social Media Platform	$\chi^2 = 0.44$	0.802	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
Age and Extent of Utilization of Social Media Platform	$r_s = 0.045$	0.597	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
Location and Extent of Utilization of Social Media Platform	$\chi^2 = 2.66$	0.264	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant

Level of significance = 0.05

Table 4 exposes the data in identifying the relationship between the profile of the students and the extent to which they utilize social media platforms as support in their academic writing. Employing the Chi-Square Test (χ^2) for sex and location and Spearman's Rank Order Correlation (r_s) for age, the data show that all p-values are greater than the level of significance (0.05). This finding will not warrant the rejection of the null hypothesis. This means there is no significant relationship between the sex, age, and location of the students and their extent of utilization of the social media platform. This connotes that the enumerated profile cannot account for their extent of utilization.

DISCUSSION

The study mainly focused on examining students' extent utilization of social media such as Facebook, YouTube, and TikTok; the perceived value of support provided by social media platforms on students' academic writing skills in grammar spelling, vocabulary, and cohesion; the significant relationship between students' extent utilization of social media platforms and its perceived value of support on their academic writing; and the significant relationship between students' extent utilization of social media platforms as support in their academic writing and the following profile items: sex, age, and location.

Students' Social Media Utilization in Supporting Their Academic Writing Skills

It can be inferred that students find social media flexible and offer a wide range of fun and interesting educational videos. As stated by Novawan et al. (2020), students enjoy the flexibility of watching videos and producing their videos for educational activities such as the submission of assignments. In line with this, McKinsey (as cited in Yunus et al., 2019), Gen Zs favor YouTube as it gives them a platform for creative expression and sharing. Moreover, it ensures permanence and reinforcement learning as students can watch and re-watch the videos may, they be lectures uploaded by the teachers or credible content creators (Nacak, 2020).

This idea aligns with David's technology acceptance model, explaining that individuals utilize technology based on its perceived usefulness. In the case of the students, their awareness of the value of support offered by the technology influenced their utilization.

Although Facebook is the top-used social media platform among Filipinos in 2022, as reported by Meltwater (2022), it placed second as the most utilized social media platform among students in terms of academic writing. It is slightly under YouTube, as shown in the table. This implies that students are still intensively utilizing Facebook as means of communication, probably because of their familiarity. To support this statement, Yunus et al. (2019) revealed that students utilized Facebook for communication as well as for learning English. Given their familiarity with Facebook, social interaction with peers, followed international artists, or content creators becomes easy; hence, it gauges their writing skills.

On the other hand, it is worth noting the considerable perceived value of support TikTok has provided to students as a learning resource for their academic writing. As the table shows, TikTok is "moderately" used by students to support their academic writing. This implies the realization of the government's effort to reinforce learning beyond the classroom through collaboration with TikTok Company (Lanuza et al., 2021).

Perceived Value of Support provided by Social Media Platforms on Students' Academic Writing Skills in Terms of Grammar

As shown in the table, students "strongly agree" with the efficacy of YouTube: (a) in checking their composition, (b) in watching tutorial videos about grammar rules, (c) in writing practice (d) in engaging in real-life discussions, and (e) in boosting confidence. These findings affirmed the statement of Yunus et al. (2019) that students write consciously of the correct language use prior to commenting, replying, and posting on social media. Likewise, Azlan and Yunus (2020) stressed that students' global exposure and exchange of information on social media allow students to monitor their own composition, hence improving their English grammatical accuracy. Social media undeniably support students' academic writing in terms of grammar, especially through videos with English grammar content, latest news written in English, shared journals, and others (Nanquil, 2020; Revesencio et al. (2022).

Perceived Value of Support provided by Social Media Platforms on Students' Academic Writing Skills in Terms of Spelling

The findings reveal that students are highly aware of the value of support social media have provided in terms of spelling. However, several studies (Sreeparvathy et al., 2022; Yap & Saludez, 2022; Gagalang, 2020) had argued the potential contribution of social media on students' linguistic proficiency. With the emergence of Send Message Short (SMS), the delivery of messages has become quick and easy. This prompts individuals to send messages on social media as quickly as possible, hence the emergence of internet language. Instead of writing the correct and proper spelling of the words, students altered the words by using acronyms or other abbreviations (Sreeparvathy et al., 2022). For instance, students would write "btw" instead of writing "by the way" (Sreeparvathy et al., 2022) and "slay" instead of writing "do your best" (Yap & Saludez, 2022). These findings imply that the habitual and persistent usage of these altered words could deteriorate English writing skills, particularly in spelling (Osman, 2021) as it could lead to fossilization (Ghouali & Benmoussat, 2019).

Perceived Value of Support provided by Social Media Platforms on Students' Academic Writing Skills in Terms of Vocabulary

Table 2.3 reflects the perceived value of support provided by social media platforms on students' academic writing skills in terms of vocabulary. As shown in the table, students perceived YouTube to have a "very high" value of support for their academic writing in terms of vocabulary, with a composite weighted mean of 4.39. This is probably because of the plentiful videos uploaded on YouTube, such as vlogs, music videos, movies, documentaries, and among others. A study by Anwas et al. (2020) affirmed that students utilized YouTube to enjoy watching music videos and movies with English vocabulary. Gradually, students believed that they naturally acquired English vocabulary. Because students often use social media due to its usefulness and ease of use, as Davis (1989) theorized, writing in English has become easier for them as they have naturally acquired English vocabulary (Novawan, 2020; Anwas et al., 2020).

On the other hand, students perceived both Facebook and TikTok to have a "high" value of support on students' academic writing skills in terms of vocabulary, with a composite weighted mean of 3.69 and 3.41, respectively. Recently, Facebook added reels to its features, which aim to widen social engagement through posting short videos, reacting, and commenting. This explains the findings by Nanquil (2020) that students gather ideas and information through vlogs, shared posts, articles, and the latest news on Facebook in English. Consequently, students have claimed that these social activities on social media broadened and improved their English vocabulary.

Moreover, these findings support the emergence of several content creators as TikTok continues to grow into a global community for people of all ages, particularly as a consequence of the pandemic (Omar & Dequan, 2020). Teachers had to use TikTok to ensure continuous instruction delivery to students (Ramakarsinin et al., 2022). TikTok is one of their found avenues, hence the rise of teachers as content creators (Paskevicius,

2021). Thus, the finding of the study also implies that students utilized social media due to its educational content, which they believed would support their English vocabulary skills.

Perceived Value of Support provided by Social Media Platforms on Students' Academic Writing Skills in Terms of Cohesion

Although the findings show that students find value of social media platforms in supporting their academic writing skills, particularly in cohesion, intensive use of shortened texts or exposure to informal writing often due to social interactions on social media might affect their composition, specifically in terms of organizing their ideas (Ghouali & Benmoussat, 2019). This is affirmed by Vygotsky's socio-cultural theory that students use language to understand and be part of the world they live in as well. Gen Z slang emerged due to the proliferating spread of reinvented and altered language on social media. Thus, students who freely embrace informal writing might potentially integrate it into their academic writing, violating the rules of Standard English (Sreeparvathy, 2022). In line with this, Gagalang (2020) revealed that the most common errors in students' academic writing are their sentence structure, the flow of ideas, redundancy, and substitution, which all fall under cohesive writing. Contrarily, Yunus et al. (2019) revealed that most students believed social media to have supported their written skills, particularly in organizing their thoughts before posting, commenting, or exchanging chats.

Overall, the findings reveal a positive awareness of students on social media utilization supporting academic writing skills; as reflected in the findings can be assumed that students utilize social media responsibly.

Relationship between the Extent to which Students Utilize Social Media Platforms and Its Perceived Value of Support on Students' Academic Writing

It can be drawn from the finding that the greater the utilization of the three social media platforms, the higher the perceived value of support in students' grammar, spelling, vocabulary, and cohesion. The study of Yunus et al. (2019) supported the current findings that social media utilization as a supplementary avenue for teaching and learning breaks the barriers to learning, thus, creating a positive learning environment. Similar findings were also manifested in the study of Novawan (2020), which claimed that YouTube provides flexibility in learning resources that support effective learning among students for both synchronous and asynchronous learning. Moreover, Putri and Aminatun (2021) asserted that social media such as Facebook allow students the exposure to practice writing. Students' grammar, spelling, vocabulary, and cohesion improve through watching videos, reading online posts, articles, and comments, as well as posting their own pieces, writing comments, and replying to chats on social media.

Relationship between the Profile of the Students and the Extent to which They Utilize Social Media Platforms as Support in Their Academic Writing Skills

As shown in the finding, there is no significant relationship between the sex, age, and location of the students and their extent of utilization of the social media platform. This connotes that the enumerated profile cannot account for their extent of utilization.

As the data shows, the extent of social media utilization is more or less the same regardless of students' sex, age, and location. These findings warranted the further improvement of the country's internet speed which becomes accessible even in rural areas. As released by Speedtest Global Index as of March 2023, the Philippine mobile median download speed is 25.63, a little faster than a couple of years, with the mobile median download speed of 25.12 in 2022 and 19.2 in 2021. As social media produce a wide range of animated tutorials and lectures about improving English writing skills, particularly in grammar, spelling, vocabulary, and cohesion, these platforms become an integral part not only for students but also for individuals who desire to learn the English language (Revesencio et al., 2022; Tus et al., 2021). Furthermore, as social media become more accessible and friendly to different ages, their influence on students learning, specifically in English proficiency, is notable.

Conclusions

Since the onset of the pandemic, individuals have realized that learning can be done beyond the classroom, especially through various digital platforms. It has then transformed the world's educational system and will continue to influence students' learning. It is apparent that college students, regardless of their background, utilize social media such as Facebook, YouTube, and TikTok due to their awareness of its educational contents which support their academic writing skills in grammar, spelling, vocabulary, and cohesion. However, social media utilization comes with greater responsibility as excessive use of these platforms can prove to be disastrous considering the proliferation of misinformation and fake news. Hence, close monitoring and guidance from teachers are necessary. Teachers should always inculcate in students the responsible use of social media.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following are hereby recommended:

Teachers:

1. Incorporate social media as educational tools into students' learning activities, such as assigning a task to read or watch in certain parameters and constructing a critique adhering to the standard academic writing.
2. Expose students to networking, which allows them to socialize, particularly the English-speaking individuals and those who play significant roles in society.

3. Create a “Classroom Publishing Portal,” where students could publish their written piece or entry, giving them the opportunity to practice their written skills at the same time be known among their classmates. The teacher holds control of the portal, provides students access, and accepts or declines students’ entries. Students’ entries could be used as one of their academic requirements quarterly or schedules determined by the teacher.

4. Design a policy for students that mandates their writings to be in essay format and free from informal language.

Administrators:

5. Foster both teachers’ and students’ academic digital literacy by conducting a quarterly seminar.

Parents:

6. Regulate access to the internet for the students’ reinforcement learning at home.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher implemented all the necessary ethical standards for the entire duration of this study. Since humans were chosen as the study’s respondents, the confidentiality of information was observed and dignity was upheld. Furthermore, minimizing potential risks to the respondents was always observed.

Throughout this study, the researcher adhered to the ethical protocols stipulated by the Ethics Committee of Foundation University to ensure that the research topic is evidently sound, significant, and ethically correct. Furthermore, the respondents of this study were requested to sign the consent form and fully understand the risks and benefits of the study being conducted.

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